

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EVOLUTION OF WOMEN’S ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE UPDATED UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article examines the essence, features and improvement of family entrepreneurship from a scientific and theoretical point of view at the new stage of development of our society. we tried to analyze from a philosophical point of view the creation, development, strengthening of social, cultural, economic and legal foundations of family entrepreneurship, as well as its significance in the development of our country.

Key words: entrepreneurship, family entrepreneurship, business, phenomenon, philosophical analysis, civil society, transformation, legalization.

At the new stage of development, it is considered to be the most organized form of family entrepreneurship in the business sector, as well as one of the important factors of economic growth. Therefore, the study of its socio-philosophical aspects on a scientific basis, paying attention to its legal aspects, the analysis of the process of becoming one of the important aspects of human (individual) activity in the period of transformation changes in society plays a theoretical, practical role. Also, the study of the present mazmu-essence, formation and development trends of family business, the need to analyze its impact on Sustainable Development has arisen. It should be noted that family entrepreneurship is a phenomenon that directly depends on the development of society, it acquires its forms and characteristics in accordance with the process of its development. Especially in this regard, it is necessary to note its dependence on the height of the human personality, activity, culture. The activities of family businesses require the establishment of laws that play an important role in their development, that is, the need for systematic improvement of its legal

foundations, the legal foundations of business and individual entrepreneurship in a modern way, in accordance with the new stage of development. The development of family entrepreneurship in the development of our country is an activity aimed at solving important social and economic problems. Also, the activities of family businesses are among the factors that favorably affect the production of goods, the competitiveness of the services rendered, the decline in youth, unemployment among the population, the decline in inflation in the economy of the country. Therefore, family entrepreneurship can play the role of a linkage between government organizations and business community, small and medium business owners. Representatives of family businesses are also important in finding solutions to organizational, legal issues between government organizations and business entities. It should be noted that the activities of family businesses should be supported by the state and other business entities, taking into account that they have become one of the main factors in its development. In particular, at the stage of innovative development, during the practice of intensive socio-democratic reforms, the adoption of special programs aimed at attracting each family member to entrepreneurship, their introduction into practice is of practical importance. In the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on family entrepreneurship" is defined as follows, "family entrepreneurship is an initiative activity carried out by family members with the aim of obtaining income (benefit) under the risk and responsibility of their own property. Family entrepreneurship is based on the voluntariness of its participants. Family business can be carried out with or without the organization of a legal entity. The organizational and legal form of family entrepreneurship, which is carried out by a legal entity, is a family enterprise. Without the organization of a legal entity, family business is carried out in accordance with the procedure established by law." [1.]

It is worth noting that the process of training young people who have completed secondary special educational institutions for the development of family entrepreneurship has been improved. Measures were taken to radically improve the activities of secondary specialized educational institutions, namely vocational colleges, technical schools and schools. In them, attention was paid to the formation

of vocational skills in the first place of young people receiving education, the educational plans of secondary special educational institutions, the number and content of subjects in them were revised. A new generation of educational-methodical literature and textbooks on the subjects studied by students of professional colleges was introduced. In them, attention was paid to the organization of educational classes on the basis of new pedagogical technologies, innovative methods, the organization of the educational process with the effective use of modern teaching techniques, explaining the main content and essence of the professions and skills taught to students. The process of training specialists of the new generation, including specialists for family business development, as well as the introduction of a new era in the social and economic development of our country, competition in the spheres of production and service, the announcement of the concept of entry of our country into the ranks of developed countries and the beginning of practical activities, that is, in developed countries, specialists put forward the need to use even more advanced methods of training. It should be noted that due to the fact that the monastery in relation to the family business in the country is shaken to the positive side, there is a need for its further improvement, as well as opportunities for the activities of these entrepreneurs, the conditions for the start-up of the family business have expanded, the assistance of state organizations In the social, economic spheres of society, necessary for those engaged in family business, the social, legal environment has completely changed, that is, the effective activity of entrepreneurs is aimed at the formation of the ri, relations between state organizations and business communities have risen to a new positive level, in accordance with the requirements of the new period.

It should be noted that at the new stage of development, the family business sector will be aimed at achieving a certain level of profit, ensuring its efficiency, the business entity that is being established, operating, that is, established in the family. In order to ensure the systematic improvement of the development of the socio-economic content of the society and, in this regard, the development of family business subjects, which is of great importance in its content, it promotes the task of

effective use of high technologies, namely information and communication and electronic methods of work. One of the characteristics inherent in the contemporary entrepreneur is their connection with their spiritual, moral, political culture together with their culture of productive use of computer technologies, modern information. As a result of this process, the information and communicative culture will be able to use its skills, ensure the commercialization of entrepreneurial activity. At the same time, the increase in the chances of professional skills in the entrepreneur, as well as the effective use of this positive Silge will ensure the competitiveness of the entrepreneur.

In the process of mastering the basics of the information and communicative culture of the representative of family entrepreneurship, the entrepreneur will have only special knowledge, skills and experience associated with the practice. Together with this, it will have the methods of studying, reasoning, applying in practice the procedures and rules adopted by the entrepreneurial communities. Also in this process, the entrepreneur gets acquainted with the content of national and universal values, learns foreign advanced technologies, finds the necessary partners for the sale of tokens produced by his enterprise, analyzes the competitive environment in the domestic and foreign markets.

In summary, an important feature in the family business, that is, when determining its position in the sphere of qualified entrepreneurship, the professional training of each businessman, the systematic development of this process, the actions that he takes to improve his skills, fulfill the place of the main criterion. Under these circumstances, it is worth noting that another time is one of the main factors in the development of family business, its connection with knowledge, an informed society. In this process, the need for the use of computer technology and telecommunication capabilities, nanotechnology, has emerged. Also, family entrepreneurship in the present tense depends on the qualification of its, that is, the entrepreneur, because as a result of professional training, the entrepreneur can find a way to solve not only in the modern business system, but also in the study of social economic problems and interests of the individual. In this process, the family entrepreneur must rely on his

creative capabilities, because as a result of such activities, the entrepreneur makes the necessary non-standard decisions for the solution of the issue, in turn, formulate the entrepreneur the opportunity to conduct activities that are resistant to the concuresia in the system of market relations.

One of the factors that play an important role for entrepreneurship is the need for this subject to have special knowledge of the sociopaths. In this process, the expansion of professional opportunities in the activities of entrepreneurs, development, modernization, acquaintance with the content of secular knowledge, which corresponds to global consciousness, is an excellent indicator of the fullness of an entrepreneurial personality. This process, in turn, provides for the formation of professional skills in the system of entrepreneurial education, independent entrepreneurs, acts as a factor confirming the competitiveness of the entrepreneur in the systems of society.

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